

CONCEPTUAL MODEL OF DEVELOPMENT COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE OF THE FUTURE TEACHER IN THE INNOVATIVE EDUCATIONAL SPACE

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Annotation: This article is devoted to the development of a conceptual model for the development of the communicative competence of the future teacher - a bachelor in an innovative educational space on the basis of a pedagogical university, based on theoretical and methodological provisions, including in different criteria.

Keywords: communicative competence, innovative education, communicative activity, concept, functional-anthropology, system-diagnostics.

КОНЦЕПТУАЛЬНАЯ МОДЕЛЬ РАЗВИТИЯ КОММУНИКАТИВНАЯ КОМПЕТЕНТНОСТЬ БУДУЩЕГО УЧИТЕЛЯ В ИННОВАЦИОННОМ ОБРАЗОВАТЕЛЬНОМ ПРОСТРАНСТВЕ

Аннотация: Данная статья посвящена разработке концептуальной модели развития коммуникативной компетентности будущего педагога - бакалавра в инновационном образовательном пространстве на базе педагогического университета, основанной на теоретико-методологических положениях, в том числе по различным критериям.

Ключевые слова: коммуникативная компетентность, инновационное образование, коммуникативная деятельность, концепция, функционально-антропология, системная диагностика.

INTRODUCTION

The development of the conceptual model of the development of the communicative competence of the future teacher-bachelor in the innovative educational space on the basis of a pedagogical university is based on theoretical and methodological provisions that include the following criteria:

1) Theoretical and methodological approaches:

- - activity;
- - functional-anthropological;
- - system-diagnostic.

2) Psychological and pedagogical theories and concepts:

- - theory of the formation and development of the personality;
- - theory of mutual relations and mutual understanding of the individual;
- - theory of professional development of personality;
- - concepts, reflecting the essential laws, principles and functions of the communicative activity of the teacher in the educational environment;
- - conceptual development of the communicative potential of the future teacher in the innovative educational space;
- - psychological and organizational-pedagogical conditions for the development of the professional communicative competence of the teacher.

The development of the professional communicative competence of the future bachelor teacher is considered by us within the knowledge of the teacher of value and personality

orientations, both in life and in the teaching profession, with the definition of one's own communicative motivation, setting the communicative goal and tasks in achieving the expected result, while realizing Regularities, communicative traditions and values in modern Uzbek education, characterized as an innovative educational space. Under the strategy of developing the professional communicative competence of the future bachelor teacher in the innovative educational space, we will understand a special complex of necessary, concrete, consistent and justified patterns of development of social processes that will:

- minimize contradictions in the professional training of a future bachelor's teacher with adequate communicative competence;
- identify the most important areas of innovation processes in the organization of teacher education;
- to ensure the achievement of the goal, which consists in the formation by the future bachelor teacher of a productive model for the development of professional communicative competence by means of inclusion in the innovative educational space.

RESEARCH MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY

It should also be noted that a number of researchers (E.A.Alisov, T.A.Andronova, M.Kuranov, Yu.N.Mikhailova, L.S.Podymova, E.A.Shmeleva, F.R.Yuzlikayev) as We have previously stressed that the educational environment is understood as the "product of relations" of all participants in the educational space. For example, in the study of Yu.N.Mikhailova it is noted that "the educational environment is one of the forms of the relationship between a person and the surrounding world. A person receiving an education does not just interact with the educational environment, he can realize himself in this interaction, mastering the culture, building social relations, involving the material of nature in the space of his own vital activity. This, the educational environment is a product of relations between the subjects of the educational space". [2,134] Researcher V.A. Yasvin defines the educational environment as a system of " influences and conditions for the formation of a personality according to a given pattern, as well as opportunities for its development contained in Social and spatial-objective environment" [3, 28]. In the educational environment, the following "components" are particularly distinguished:

- psychodactical (content, forms and methods of activity);
- social component (relations arising between subjects);
- space-object component (opportunities for organization of activities and development of students, provided by the subject environment);
- subjects of the environment".

With regard to the definition of the essence of the innovative educational environment, the researchers E.A.Alisov and L.S.Podymova note that one of its distinctive features is "the synthesis of the fundamental factors of the development of the individual - the environment of life activity, education, self-education and self-education aimed at realizing the creative potential Student". [1,63] Such an environment is a complex form of functioning and implementation of the fundamental principles of innovative pedagogy and is a unified educational space of the educational institution that allows cooperating the efforts of all stakeholders and objects in the qualitative preparation of future specialists.

In the work of T.A.Andronova it is noted that "innovation itself is an object (the result of intellectual activity, product, object) as well as significant changes in the social and material environment obtained during the commercialization of objects of scientific and technical and other activities containing new , Including scientific knowledge, created to meet social needs and (or)

profit". In the research work of E.A.Shmeleva, it is noted that "the formation of the innovation environment is aimed at developing the innovative potential necessary for generating new ideas, creating new products, technologies, promoting fundamental and applied research in various fields of knowledge, including pedagogical. On the development of innovative activity of the individual as the main criterion of readiness for innovative activity in the professional sphere"[4, 14]. And besides, one of the most actual characteristics for our time, ozhet be a statement about the innovative way of development of society as a dominant, because "in today's competition in the first place is not a struggle for resources, material goods, and for the ability to innovate".

RESEARCH RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Thus, summarizing the wide range of different approaches to the conceptualization of the very concept of "innovation" available in the scientific and methodological literature, we can distinguish a list of its main characteristics (Fig. 1.1)

Figure 1 Characteristics of the concept of "innovation"

Specificity of the activity of a higher educational institution determines the following possible sources of innovation:

1. Existing idea, not found practical implementation.
2. There is a practical approach that does not have a theoretical basis, but the creation of which will fill the old methods with new meaning, making them more effective, expanding the scope of their application.
3. The existing practical methodology, previously not implemented in the pedagogical process of a higher educational institution.
4. Original educational ideas or new, more promising generalizations of pre-existing ideas.
6. Practical implementation of educational innovations.

Based on the research done, we propose a structural conceptual model of the communicative competence of the future bachelor's teacher, including cognitive, praxeological and axiological components, developed by us and presented in the form of schematic components (Fig. 1.2), (Fig. 1.3) and (Fig. 1.4).

Fig. 1.2. The cognitive component of the structural model

The student is ready to make a model of the forthcoming communication, defining participants in it, the content, methods and means of its implementation, developing a plan of adequate actions	
The student is able to clearly, competently and consistently present his ideas on the issue under discussion	
The student is able to reasonably and reasonably discuss on any topic, and has the readiness to teach this to others	
The student is able to use various available methods (verbal, graphic, symbolic) for illustration, interpretation, argumentation and proof	
The student is able to obtain the information necessary for him from various sources (books, newspapers, electronic textbooks, the Internet, etc.)	
The student is able to independently and in a timely manner to perform a certain self-control of the communication process, with the fulfillment of the plan he has planned in accordance with the goals set and the intermediate results obtained	
The student is ready to reflect the available communicative activity, namely, to analyze the received results of communication, to identify deviations from the model, to characterize the involvement of other subjects of communication in the	
The student is able to identify the conditions that ensure the effective organization of the communication process	

The presented schematic structures of the communicative competence of the student - the future teacher-bachelor, we consider as a conceptual basis for the development of educational programs in many academic disciplines. Summing up, we would also like to note that the considered innovative approaches and the corresponding educational models can contribute to the solution of certain urgent tasks of modern higher education, namely: effective mastering of knowledge by students; Formation of practical research skills, allowing students to make professional decisions; Independent search by students for research activities; Increase of cognitive activity; Formation of value orientations of the individual; Development of creative abilities with the creation of didactic and psychological conditions conducive to the successful full-fledged adaptation of students in teaching activities

CONCLUSION

Considering the actual problem of the formation of communicative competence for future bachelor teachers, it is necessary to note the connection with the transition of pedagogical education to the multilevel training of qualified specialists that are in tune with the requirements of modern society for the profession of the teacher. In the process of research analysis, it was established that the existing traditional educational system for professional and pedagogical training of bachelors in a pedagogical university is not able to fully ensure the effective formation and development of the professional and personal quality of the teacher, referred to as communicative competence. It should be noted that modern requirements for the preparation of students - future teachers, are changing rapidly, because society needs not just a professional teacher, but also a competent specialist who has a variety of teaching methods using innovative technologies. In connection with this provision, the effective preparation of bachelor teachers for their future teaching activities plays a crucial role today.

Our research allowed us to make the following general conclusions: the essence and structure of the concept of "communicative competence" was clarified and supplemented, with the rationale for its phased formation in the future bachelor's teacher; A graduate of a teacher training university should always be in demand on the labor market, and for this it needs to learn quickly and productively solve professional problems, showing activity, flexibility and ability to work; the most important indicators of the formation of communicative competence of teachers should be: general and professional knowledge, skills and skills, as well as mandatory readiness for independent pedagogical activity, with an indispensable need for creative development.

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